

The impact of spatial variability in soil nitrogen and the value in its management: A case study

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Abstract

Variable rate nitrogen (VRN) management strategies seek to optimise the nitrogen (N) supply to match crop demand, both to maximise farmer profitability and minimise environmental risks. Despite potential benefits, there has been comparatively little work looking at the value proposition underpinning VRN. Gridded soil samples from a cropping paddock in Hawke's Bay, New Zealand, were characterised for residual mineral N and a bioassay used to quantify N mineralisation potential. These data were used in APSIM, a systems model, to estimate production outcomes under three different N management strategies in an irrigated and non-irrigated maize cropping system. Predictions showed that yield was comparable between management scenarios, while VRN resulted in lower residual soil N at harvest for both irrigated and non-irrigated systems. While these results are for a single paddock, they demonstrate that in this circumstance the implementation of VRN significantly improved environmental outcomes without impacting gross margins.

Background

Nutrient management in agricultural systems can have a significant impact on profitability and environmental outcomes. The oversupply of N fertilisers for plant growth is economically wasteful and unused soil mineral N is susceptible to nitrate (NO₃) leaching, which in turn reduces freshwater quality. In the converse, the undersupply of mineral N can result in crop N stress, reduce yield and lower profitability. It is therefore important that when determining N fertiliser application rates, the existing soil N pools — residual mineral N and future soil N supply — are taken into account in the N balance.

In general, common practice in cropping systems is to manage a field or management unit homogeneously, assuming no spatial variability in either source of soil N supply. This however is often not true, and spatial variability, to varying degrees, does exist due to soil type, residues or previous management. As a result, even if the existing soil N pools are accounted for on a representative whole field basis, this can result in areas that receive too much or too little fertiliser N.

One proposed solution to managing this variability is VRN management strategies, which seek to optimise the N supply to match crop demand spatially, both to maximise farmer profitability and minimise environmental risks. Despite potential benefits, there has been comparatively little work addressing the value proposition underpinning VRN and understanding the importance of the spatial variability in soil N pools in N management.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to determine, through modelling, the impact of managing nutrients spatially using a case study approach.

Methods

Gridded soil samples (n = 105, 0–15 cm depth) from a cropping paddock in Hawke's Bay, New Zealand, were characterised for residual mineral N and a greenhouse bioassay used to quantify how much N was supplied to a sink crop over a 3 month period. These data were used in APSIM Next Generation, a systems model (Holzworth et al., 2014), to estimate production outcomes under different N management strategies in a maize grain cropping system over 35 field seasons.

Three management scenarios were tested (Historical practice, Good management practice and VRN), reflecting a range of basic to advanced approaches to managing fertiliser. Both irrigated and unirrigated crops were considered. For each scenario an N balance was constructed at each sampling location using different levels of information on the size of the N pools and that targeted a maximum yield potential of 95% but minimised the end of season mineral N. N fertiliser application was then calculated accordingly. A quarter of fertiliser N requirement was applied at sowing and the remaining as a side dressing at 7 weeks from emergence.

- Historical practice: Manage N balance of each sampling location with a common approach used historically — no knowledge of residual mineral N or potential within crop soil N supply. Forty-five kg/N/ha at sowing and 185 kg/N/ha side dressing at 7 weeks from emergence was applied.
- Good management practice: Manage N balance at each sampling location with an awareness of paddock means for residual mineral N and potential within crop soil N supply.
- Variable rate N (VRN): Manage N balance at each sampling location with location-specific residual mineral N and potential within crop soil N supply.

The primary outputs from the modelling study for each sampling location were grain yield (t/ha), gross margin (\$/ha) and residual NO₃ of the soil profile (kg/ha), a risk factor for winter leaching.

To calculate the gross margin, basic input costs were used (Pioneer Guide, 2017). It was assumed that no lime was applied and a basic soil test was considered to cost \$10/ha. Irrigation costs were \$2.17/mm/ha (FAR, 2013). Fertiliser was based on grower practice of applying di-ammonium phosphate (DAP) at planting and a urea side-dress using listed prices obtained from Ravensdown Fertiliser Co-operative (2017). Application costs were based on the Pioneer Guide (2017). Cartage and drying costs are based on the wet yield of maize, but the APSIM yield output is in units of dry weight. To enable calculation of cartage and drying costs, the APSIM yield was corrected for a moisture content of 22% (Wilson 1995; Pioneer Guide, 2017). Cartage cost were based on this moisture corrected yield and for an assumed distance of 50 km. Drying costs were based on the Pioneer Guide (2017) recommendations to achieve a moisture content of 14%. An average price of \$363/t of dried grain was used to estimate the value of the crop (Agri HQ, 2017).

Results

Key measures of soil N pools were highly variable among samples, with variance observed in soil N and carbon analysis prior to the assay and in the amount of N mineralised through the assay. Initial mineral N ranged from 0.020 to 0.109 with a median of 0.056 g N/kg dry soil. The pot mineralisation assay resulted in the release of a further 0.0081 to 0.1873 with a median of 0.0765 g N/kg dry soil over 3 months.

Modelled outputs showed that yield was comparable between the three management scenarios considered (Table 1), and irrigation resulted in high yields than unirrigated. In contrast, the Historical practice scenario had consistently higher residual soil N at harvest, irrespective of irrigation practice, compared to other scenarios. VRN resulted in lower residual soil N at harvest and higher gross margins than Good management practice for both irrigated and non-irrigated systems.

Table 1. Mean grain yield, gross margin and remaining soil profile nitrate (NO₃; 0–2 m) at harvest for irrigated and unirrigated management of the three scenarios (Historical practice, Good management practice, Variable rate nitrogen (VRN)), based on 35 years of simulations.

Scenario	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Mean gross margin (\$/ha)		Mean soil profile NO ₃ (kg/ha)	
	Unirrigated	Irrigated	Unirrigated	Irrigated	Unirrigated	Irrigated
Historical practice	13.5	14.6	2465	2669	149.2	144.6
Good management practice	13.2	14.3	2462	2705	86.6	76.8
VRN	13.3	14.5	2508	2779	80.5	69.3

When mapped spatially, for unirrigated scenarios, the Historical practice and VRN showed very little spatial variation in mean maize grain yield, while the Good Management Practice approach tended to have areas of the paddock with lower mean yields (Figure 1). For mean soil NO₃ at harvest, the Historical practice had significant spatial variability with some areas of the paddock having in excess of 200 kg/ha (Figure 2). Good Management Practice had similar variability, however absolute values were lower, while VRN minimised spatial variation in mean soil NO₃.

Figure 1. Spatial variability across the study site in mean modelled maize grain yield (t/ha) for unirrigated scenarios, based on 35 years of simulations

Discussion

While these results are for a single paddock, they demonstrate that the implementation of VRN can significantly improve environmental outcomes without impacting gross margins. Further benefits could be achieved by managing this variability temporally. This study does not consider the practical implications of sampling and testing soil characteristics to fine a degree of resolution, or the spatial application of N fertilisers.

Conclusion

Understanding the initial mineral N status and mineralisation potential of a field at a rich spatial density could improve key production outcomes.

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Figure 2. Spatial variability across the study site in mean modelled soil nitrate (NO₃; kg/ha, 0–2 m) at harvest for unirrigated scenarios, based on 35 years of simulations

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